

PUPILS' AWARENESS OF COMPREHENSIVE SEXUAL EDUCATION: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the level of awareness of Grade VI pupils on comprehensive sexuality education in the West District of Dipolog City Division during the academic year 2023–2024. Specifically, it determined the respondents' profile in terms of age and sex, assessed their level of awareness, and examined whether significant differences exist when grouped according to their profile. The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design using a researcher-made questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.8559. A total of 242 respondents were selected from a population of 650 pupils using proportionate sampling. Findings revealed that the majority of respondents were aged 11–12 years old and were predominantly female. The overall level of awareness on comprehensive sexuality education was described as “Agree,” indicating a moderate level of awareness. Pupils demonstrated awareness of basic concepts; however, gaps were noted in areas such as contraception, communication with trusted adults, and external influencing factors. Cultural taboos and stigma were identified as significant barriers to open discussion and awareness. Furthermore, no significant difference was found in awareness when respondents were grouped according to age, while a significant difference was observed when grouped according to sex. The study concludes that although pupils possess a moderate level of awareness, there is a need to enhance comprehensive sexuality education through age-appropriate, gender-responsive, and culturally sensitive interventions. Strengthening school-based programs, teacher training, and parental involvement is recommended to improve pupils' knowledge and promote responsible behavior.

Keywords: *comprehensive sexuality education, awareness, Grade VI pupils, adolescence, Dipolog City*

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents today are becoming increasingly aware of their sexuality and physical identity, shaped by rapid social, cultural, and technological changes. As inherently social beings, individuals develop knowledge, perceptions, and behaviors through interaction with their environment, particularly during critical developmental stages such as puberty. This stage, typically occurring between ages 11 to 16, marks significant biological and psychological changes, including sexual maturation and heightened curiosity about sexuality (Datinggaling & Chua, 2023; Agustin et al., 2017). With the rise of digital platforms, young people increasingly use social media as a space for self-expression and identity exploration, which significantly influences their attitudes and overall well-being. In response, schools have begun integrating sexuality education into their curricula to guide learners in developing appropriate knowledge, skills, and values that promote health, dignity, and responsible decision-making (Lafontan et al., 2024).

Sex education in schools has become a vital component of holistic education, as it addresses not only biological aspects of sex but also emotional, psychological, and social dimensions of human development. Adolescents' natural curiosity, when combined with limited or inaccurate information, may lead to risky behaviors such as early sexual engagement and unprotected intercourse. Research suggests that comprehensive sexuality education plays a crucial role in preventing such outcomes by equipping learners with accurate knowledge and guiding them toward safer sexual practices. Notably, comprehensive programs do not increase sexual activity among youth; instead, they promote informed choices and protective behaviors (Lafontan et al., 2024; Agustin et al., 2017). Furthermore, school-based sexuality education increases awareness of child sexual abuse and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), helping to safeguard adolescents' physical and emotional well-being.

Education remains a key driver of individual and national development, contributing to improved literacy, social welfare, and economic growth. Within this broader context, sexuality education is essential in addressing public health concerns, particularly the rising incidence of STIs among adolescents. Despite increased global awareness, infection rates continue to rise, especially in developing countries where cultural and religious beliefs often limit open discussions about sexual health (Pasay-an et al., 2024; Tanaka et al., 2017). Adolescents often rely on peers or unreliable online sources for information, which can further increase their vulnerability to misinformation and risky behaviors (Agustin et al., 2017).

In the Philippines, adolescent sexual and reproductive health issues remain a significant concern. The country continues to experience increasing cases of early pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections among young people, influenced by factors such as poverty, religious beliefs, and limited access to comprehensive sexuality education (Gunchi et al., 2018). Although the government has mandated the integration of sexuality education into the curriculum through the Reproductive Health Law, its implementation remains challenging due to the country's conservative cultural context

(Baria et al., 2024). Additionally, discussions about sexuality are often considered taboo within families, resulting in limited parent-child communication. Studies indicate that while many parents are aware of sexuality education, a large proportion are hesitant to discuss it with their children, further contributing to gaps in knowledge (Baria et al., 2024; Datinggaling & Chua, 2023).

Moreover, the increasing prevalence of premarital sexual engagement among Filipino youth—leading to unintended pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and STIs—has become an alarming social issue requiring urgent intervention (Gulane et al., 2022). Sexuality education is therefore recognized globally as an essential strategy for addressing these challenges, as it enables young people to acquire accurate information, develop responsible attitudes, and build skills necessary for making informed decisions about their sexual health and relationships. However, the effectiveness of such programs depends largely on teachers' competence, parental support, and the overall implementation of school-based initiatives (Cabreros, 2022).

Given these circumstances, there is a pressing need to assess learners' level of awareness regarding comprehensive sexuality education. Understanding pupils' knowledge and perceptions is essential in identifying gaps and informing appropriate interventions. Hence, this study aimed to investigate the level of awareness of Grade VI pupils on comprehensive sexual education in the West District of Dipolog City Division during the academic year 2023–2024. The findings of this study will serve as a basis for developing an intervention program designed to enhance awareness, promote responsible behavior, and support the overall well-being of learners.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate pupils' awareness on comprehensive sexual education, this academic year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age; and
 - 1.2. Sex?
2. What is the level of pupils' awareness on comprehensive sexual education?
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of pupils' awareness on comprehensive sexual education when analyzed according to their profile?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to determine the level of awareness of Grade VI pupils regarding comprehensive sexuality education. The descriptive approach was appropriate because it focuses on describing existing

conditions, perceptions, and behaviors without manipulating variables or establishing causal relationships. It allowed the researcher to systematically gather quantifiable data reflecting the current awareness of the respondents.

The participants of the study were Grade VI pupils from selected public elementary schools in the West District of Dipolog City Division. Out of a total population of 650 pupils, a sample size of 242 respondents was determined using the sample size formula for proportions, with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. Proportionate sampling was utilized to ensure equitable representation from each participating school, with the sample distribution based on each school's population size relative to the total population.

A researcher-made questionnaire was used as the primary data-gathering instrument. The instrument was carefully constructed to measure pupils' awareness of comprehensive sexuality education and was subjected to content validation by experts. To ensure reliability, the questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.8559, which indicates high internal consistency and confirms that the instrument was dependable for use in the study.

Prior to data collection, the researcher secured formal permission from the school principals and Grade VI advisers of the participating schools. Upon approval, the questionnaires were personally administered to the selected respondents, and clear instructions were provided to facilitate accurate responses. After the completion of the survey, the questionnaires were retrieved, organized, and tabulated. The collected data were then submitted to a statistician for appropriate statistical treatment.

Ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the research process. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. The researcher ensured that no harm was inflicted on the participants and that their privacy was protected at all times. All data collected were treated with strict confidentiality, and the instruments used in the study were properly disposed of after the completion of the research.

Finally, the data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools. The level of awareness of the respondents was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, and the results were interpreted based on corresponding descriptive equivalents to determine the overall level of awareness on comprehensive sexuality education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the responses of the randomly selected two-hundred forty-two (242) Grade 6 pupils of West District, Dipolog City Division. The responses were treated statistically in order to answer the research questions of the present investigation.

Table 1.
Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Respondents' Age	Frequency	Percentage
10 years old and below	-	-
11 – 12 years old	216	89.26
13 – 14 years old	25	10.33
15 years old and above	1	0.41
Total	242	100.00%

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents according to age. The data show that the majority of the respondents, 216 or 89.26%, are aged 11–12 years old, indicating that most of the Grade VI pupils fall within the expected age range for their grade level. Meanwhile, 25 respondents or 10.33% belong to the 13–14 years old group, suggesting the presence of slightly older learners, possibly due to delayed school entry or grade repetition. Only 1 respondent or 0.41% is 15 years old and above, while no respondents fall under the 10 years old and below category. These findings imply that the respondents are predominantly in their early adolescent stage, a developmental period typically associated with significant physical, emotional, and cognitive changes. This age distribution is appropriate for the study, as learners within this stage are beginning to develop curiosity and awareness about issues related to sexuality and personal identity. Hence, their responses are relevant in assessing awareness of comprehensive sexuality education. In support, Datinggaling and Chua (2023) identifies ages 10–13 as a stage marked by significant physical, emotional, and cognitive changes, including the onset of puberty and increased identity exploration. Filipino adolescents at this stage are also described as developing heightened curiosity about self, relationships, and sexuality, making them receptive to sexuality education.

Table 2.
Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Respondents' Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	106	43.80
Female	136	56.20
Total	242	100.00%

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents according to sex. The data reveal that out of the total 242 Grade VI pupils, 136 or 56.20% are female, while 106 or 43.80% are male. This indicates that the majority of the respondents in the study are female. The results suggest a slightly higher representation of female pupils compared to male pupils among the participants. This imbalance, although not large, may reflect the actual enrollment distribution in the selected schools or the availability of respondents during data collection. Thus, both sexes are adequately represented, allowing for a balanced perspective in analyzing the level of awareness on comprehensive sexuality education.

In support, Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2022) stressing the fact that the slightly higher representation of female pupils is consistent with Philippine educational data showing that females often have higher enrollment and retention rates than males in basic education. This trend explains their greater availability during data collection while still maintaining near gender parity, ensuring balanced representation in studies

Table 3

Level of Awareness on Comprehensive Sexual Education Among the Respondents

Level of Awareness on Comprehensive Sexual Education Among The Respondents	AWV	Verbal Description
1. Awareness among Grade 6 pupils regarding comprehensive sexual education may be limited to biological aspects such as puberty, menstruation, and reproductive organs.	4.11	Agree
2. Some Grade 6 pupils may have misconceptions or limited understanding about topics like contraception, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and consent.	3.19	Neither Agree nor Disagree
3. Awareness about gender identity and sexual orientation may be limited among Grade 6 pupils, depending on the inclusivity of their school curriculum and community environment.	3.65	Agree
4. Grade 6 pupils may receive information about healthy relationships, respect, and consent, but the depth of understanding may vary.	3.62	Agree
5. Awareness about the importance of communication with trusted adults regarding sexual health matters may vary among Grade 6 pupils.	3.24	Neither Agree nor Disagree
6. Awareness among Grade 6 pupils regarding LGBTQ+ issues and rights may be influenced by the inclusivity of their school environment and community attitudes.	3.42	Agree
7. Factors such as parental involvement, peer influence, and exposure to media may also shape Grade 6 pupils' awareness of sexual education topics.	3.06	Neither Agree nor Disagree
8. Cultural taboos and stigma surrounding discussions about sex may inhibit open dialogue and awareness among Grade 6 pupils.	4.17	Agree
9. School-based activities such as seminars, workshops, and peer education programs can enhance Grade 6 pupils' awareness and understanding of comprehensive sexual education.	3.42	Agree

Mean	3.54	Agree
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Table 4 displays the respondents' degree of awareness on comprehensive sexual education. The data from the table indicates that a majority of the participants acknowledge that cultural taboos and social stigma related to discussing sex can hinder open communication and awareness among Grade 6 students. This aspect received an average weighted value of 4.17. In comparison, the average weighted value for comprehensive sexual education focusing solely on biological aspects such as puberty, menstruation, and reproductive organs was 4.11. It is worth noting that there was no clear consensus on whether participants agreed or disagreed with this statement. Parental participation, peer influence, and exposure to media are factors that may impact Grade 6 students' understanding of sexual education themes. These factors have an average weighted value of 3.06. The average value for this facet is 3.54, which may be regarded as agreement. The findings emphasized that the majority of respondents acknowledge that cultural taboos and stigma surrounding discussions about sex can hinder open dialogue and awareness among Grade 6 students. This suggests that the level of awareness regarding comprehensive sexual education among Grade 6 students is limited due to cultural taboos and stigma surrounding discussions about sex, which negatively affects the level of awareness among these young individuals. Gulane et al. (2020) emphasize the significance of tackling cultural taboos and stigma related to talks about sex in order to enhance the degree of knowledge about comprehensive sexual education among Grade 6 students. The statement underscores the need of using culturally sensitive and age-appropriate methods in sexual education that respect varied cultural origins while offering accurate information and assistance to young folks.

Table 4

Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Awareness on Comprehensive Sexual Education Among Respondents When Analyzed According to their Profile

Profile	Level of Awareness on Comprehensive Sexual Education				
	U-Value	H-Value	p-value @ 0.05	Action	Interpretation
Age		2.9627	0.2273	Ho Accepted	No Significant Difference
Sex	8690.5		0.005971	Ho Rejected	Significant Difference

* p-value is lesser than 0.05 level of significance = significant; Reject Ho

* p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significant = not significant; Accept Ho.

Table 4 presents the test of significant difference in the level of awareness on comprehensive sexual education when respondents are grouped according to age and sex. The results show that age has no significant difference in awareness (H = 2.9627, p = 0.2273), since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the level of awareness among respondents is relatively similar regardless of their age

group. This finding is supported by local studies which indicate that adolescents within close age ranges tend to have comparable exposure to information sources such as school curricula, peers, and media, resulting in similar levels of awareness (San Gabriel, 2023). Such findings suggest that age alone may not significantly influence awareness when learners belong to the same developmental stage and educational level.

On the other hand, the results reveal that sex has a significant difference in the level of awareness ($U = 8690.5$, $p = 0.005971$), as the p -value is less than 0.05. This indicates that male and female respondents differ in their awareness of comprehensive sexual education. This finding is supported by recent Philippine studies which show that gender differences influence knowledge, attitudes, and awareness related to sexuality and health education, with variations often linked to socialization, access to information, and gender roles (Gulane et al., 2020). Additionally, gender-based experiences and societal expectations shape how learners receive and process sexuality-related information, leading to observable differences between males and females.

Thus, the table implies that while age does not significantly affect awareness among Grade VI pupils, sex plays a crucial role in shaping differences in awareness levels. This highlights the importance of implementing gender-responsive sexuality education programs that address the specific needs and perspectives of both male and female learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were drawn.

First, the majority of the respondents are within the age range of 11–12 years old, indicating that they belong to the early adolescent stage. This suggests that the participants are at a critical developmental period characterized by increasing curiosity and awareness about sexuality and personal identity, making them appropriate respondents for the study.

Second, there is a slightly higher proportion of female respondents compared to male respondents. However, the difference is minimal, indicating that both sexes are adequately represented in the study. This ensures that the findings reflect a balanced perspective in assessing pupils' awareness of comprehensive sexual education.

Third, the overall level of awareness of Grade VI pupils on comprehensive sexual education is generally at the level of "Agree," indicating a moderate level of awareness. While pupils demonstrate awareness of basic concepts such as biological aspects and the influence of cultural taboos, there are still areas where understanding is limited, particularly on more complex topics such as contraception, communication with trusted adults, and external influencing factors.

Fourth, cultural taboos and stigma surrounding discussions about sex were identified as major factors that hinder open communication and awareness among pupils. This implies that socio-cultural barriers continue to affect the effectiveness of sexuality education among young learners.

Finally, the test of significant difference revealed that age does not significantly influence the level of awareness, indicating that pupils within the same developmental stage tend to have similar levels of understanding. However, sex was found to have a significant effect, suggesting that male and female pupils differ in their awareness of comprehensive sexual education. This implies the need for gender-responsive approaches in delivering sexuality education program.

Hence, the study concludes that while Grade VI pupils possess a moderate level of awareness on comprehensive sexual education, there remain important gaps that need to be addressed through more inclusive, age-appropriate, and culturally sensitive educational interventions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

First, schools should strengthen the implementation of comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) by ensuring that topics go beyond biological aspects and include discussions on contraception, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), consent, gender identity, and healthy relationships. Instruction should be age-appropriate, accurate, and developmentally suitable for early adolescents.

Second, teachers should be provided with continuous training and capacity-building programs to enhance their knowledge, confidence, and skills in delivering sexuality education. This will ensure that educators are well-equipped to handle sensitive topics effectively and professionally.

Third, school administrators should organize seminars, workshops, and peer education programs to further enhance pupils' awareness and understanding of sexual health. These activities may also include guidance sessions that promote open communication and safe learning environments.

Fourth, parents and guardians should be encouraged to actively participate in their children's learning by fostering open and supportive communication at home regarding sexuality and health-related concerns. Parent orientation programs may be conducted to reduce discomfort and improve their ability to guide their children.

Fifth, curriculum developers and policymakers should design and implement gender-responsive sexuality education programs that consider the differing needs,

perspectives, and experiences of male and female learners, as the study revealed significant differences based on sex.

Sixth, efforts should be made to address cultural taboos and stigma surrounding discussions of sexuality by promoting awareness campaigns and community-based programs that encourage openness while respecting cultural values.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to conduct further studies involving larger samples, different grade levels, or other variables such as socio-economic status, parental education, and access to media, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing pupils' awareness of sexuality education.

These recommendations aim to enhance the effectiveness of sexuality education and contribute to the development of informed, responsible, and healthy young individuals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained from the school principals and relevant authorities of the participating schools. The purpose, procedures, and significance of the study were clearly explained to ensure transparency and understanding.

Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Informed consent was secured from the respondents, and assent procedures appropriate for minors were observed. The respondents were given the freedom to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any point without any form of penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained throughout the research process. No personally identifiable information was collected, and all responses were treated with strict confidentiality. The data gathered were used solely for academic and research purposes and were stored securely to prevent unauthorized access.

The researcher ensured that no harm—physical, psychological, or emotional—was inflicted on the participants. The questionnaire was carefully designed to be age-appropriate and sensitive to the respondents' developmental level. Furthermore, all collected data and research instruments were properly disposed of after the completion of the study to maintain data privacy and security.

In addition, the researcher ensured academic integrity by properly acknowledging all sources cited in the study. Where applicable, ethical use of digital tools, including AI-assisted technologies, was observed to support writing, analysis, and organization of the research without compromising originality, accuracy, and scholarly responsibility.

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